

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 38

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 38

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 38:0 A Psalm of David, for a memorial.</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד לְהַזְכִּיר : 2 יְהוָה</p>
<p>Psa. 38:1 O LORD, ^arebuke me not in Your wrath,</p>	<p>אֶל-בְּקַצְפֶּךָ תוֹכִיחֵנִי וּבְחַמְתֶּךָ תִּיַסְרֵנִי : 3 כִּי-חֲצִיךָ נִחְתּוּ בִּי</p>
<p>And chasten me not in Your burning anger.</p>	<p>וּתְנַחַת עָלַי יְדֶךָ : 4 אֵין-מָתָם</p>
<p>² For Your ^aarrows have sunk deep into me,</p>	<p>בְּבִשְׂרֵי מִפְּנֵי זַעֲמֶךָ אֵין-שָׁלוֹם</p>
<p>And ^bYour hand has pressed down on me.</p>	<p>בְּעֲצָמַי מִפְּנֵי חֲטָאתִי : 5 כִּי עֲזַנְתִּי עָבְרוּ רַאשֵׁי כַּמְשָׂא כְּבֹד</p>
<p>³ There is ^ano soundness in my flesh ^bbecause of Your indignation;</p>	<p>וּכְבֹדוֹ מִמֶּנִּי : 6 הַבְּאִישׁוֹ נִמְקוּ</p>
<p>There is no health ^ain my bones because of my sin.</p>	<p>חֲבוּרָתִי מִפְּנֵי אֲוִלָּתִי : 7 נִעְוִינִי</p>
<p>⁴ For my ^ainiquities are gone over my head;</p>	<p>שִׁחַתִּי עַד-מְאֹד כָּל-הַיּוֹם קָרַד</p>
<p>As a heavy burden they weigh too much for me.</p>	<p>הֶלְכָתִי : 8 כִּי-כֶסֶלִי מָלְאוּ</p>
<p>⁵ My ¹wounds grow foul <i>and</i> fester Because of ^amy folly.</p>	<p>נִקְלָה וְאֵין מָתָם בְּבִשְׂרֵי : 9 נַפְוִגוֹתַי וְנֹדְכֹתַי עַד-מְאֹד</p>
<p>⁶ I am bent over and ^agreatly bowed down;</p>	<p>שָׂאֲגֹתַי מִנְהַמַּת לִבִּי : 10 אֲדַנִּי</p>
<p>I ^bgo mourning all day long.</p>	<p>נִגְדָךְ כָּל-תְּאוֹתַי וְאֲנַחְתִּי מִמֶּךָ</p>
<p>⁷ For my loins are filled with ^aburning,</p>	<p>לֹא-נִסְתָּרָה : 11 לִבִּי סִחַרְחַר</p>
<p>And there is ^bno soundness in my flesh.</p>	<p>עֲזַבְנִי כַחֲוִי וְאוֹר-עֵינַי גַּם-אֵהֶם</p>
<p>⁸ I am ^abenumbed and ¹badly crushed;</p>	<p>אֵין אֶתִּי : 12 אֶהְבִּי וְרַעִי מִנְּגִיד</p>
<p>I ^{2b}groan because of the ³agitation of my heart.</p>	<p>נִגְעֵי יַעֲמֹדוּ וְקָרוּבֵי מִרְתַּק עֲמָדוֹ : 13 וַיִּנְקָשׁוּ אִמְבִּקְשֵׁי</p>
<p>Psa. 38:9 Lord, all ^amy desire is ¹before You;</p> <p>And my ^bsighing is not hidden from You.</p>	<p>נִפְשֵׁי וְדַרְשֵׁי רַעְתִּי דִבְרוּ תְּהוֹת</p>

¹⁰ My heart throbs, “my strength fails me;

And the ^blight of my eyes, even ¹that ²has gone from me.

¹¹ My ^{1a}loved ones and my friends stand aloof from my plague;

And my kinsmen ^bstand afar off.

¹² Those who “seek my life ^blay snares for me;

And those who “seek to injure me have ¹threatened destruction,

And they ^ddevise treachery all day long.

Psa. 38:13 But I, like a deaf man, do not hear;

And *I am* like a “mute man who does not open his mouth.

¹⁴ Yes, I am like a man who does not hear,

And in whose mouth are no arguments.

¹⁵ For ^aI ¹hope in You, O LORD; You ^bwill answer, O Lord my God.

¹⁶ For I said, “May they not rejoice over me,

Who, when my foot slips, “would magnify themselves against me.”

¹⁷ For I am “ready to fall, And ^bmy ¹sorrow is continually

before me.

¹⁸ For I ^{1a}confess my iniquity; I am full of ^banxiety because of my sin.

¹⁹ But my “enemies are vigorous *and* ¹strong,

And many are those who ^bhate me wrongfully.

²⁰ And those who “repay evil for good,

וּמְרִמּוֹת כָּל-הַיּוֹם יִהְיוּ : ¹⁴

וְאֲנִי כִחֲרַשׁ לֹא אֶשְׁמַע וְכֹאֲלִים

לֹא יִפְתַּח-פִּי : ¹⁵ וְאֱהִי כְאִישׁ

אֲשֶׁר לֹא-שָׁמַע וְאֵין בְּפִיו

תּוֹכְחוֹת : ¹⁶ כִּי-לֵן יִהְיֶה

הוֹחֲלֹתִי אֶתָּה תִעַנֶּה אֶדְנִי

אֱלֹהֵי : ¹⁷ כִּי-אֶמְרֹתִי פֶן-

יִשְׁמַח־לִי בְמוֹט רַגְלִי עָלַי

הַגְּדִילוּ : ¹⁸ כִּי-אֲנִי לְצַלַּע נֶכּוֹן

וּמְכֹאֲבֵי נִגְדֵי תָמִיד : ¹⁹ כִּי-

עוֹנֵי אֲנִיד אֲדַאֵג מִחַטָּאתַי : ²⁰

וְאֵיבֵי תֵיִם עֲצָמוּ וְרִבּוֹ שִׁנְאֵי

שָׁקֵר : ²¹ וּמִשְׁלָמֵי רָעָה תַחַת

טוֹבָה יִשְׁטַנּוּנֵי תַחַת רְדוּפֵי-

[רְדָפֵי]-טוֹב : ²² אֶל-הַעֲזִבְנֵי

יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי אֶל-תִּרְתַּק מִמֶּנִּי :

²³ תּוֹשָׁה לְעִזְרֹתֵי אֶדְנִי

תִּשׁוּעָתִי :

They ^boppose me, because I follow
what is good.

²¹ Do not forsake me, O LORD;
O my God, ^ado not be far from
me!

²² Make ^ahaste to help me,
O Lord, ^bmy salvation!

References

<p>Psalm 38:1 ^aPs 6:1</p> <p>Psalm 38:2 ^aJob 6:4 ^bPs 32:4</p> <p>Psalm 38:3 ^aIs 1:6 ^bPs 102:10 ^cJob 33:19; Ps 6:2; 31:10</p> <p>Psalm 38:4 ^aEzra 9:6; Ps 40:12</p> <p>Psalm 38:5 ¹Or <i>stripes</i> ^aPs 69:5</p> <p>Psalm 38:6 ^aPs 35:14 ^bJob 30:28; Ps 42:9; 43:2</p> <p>Psalm 38:7 ^aPs 102:3 ^bPs 38:3</p> <p>Psalm 38:8 ¹Or <i>greatly</i> ²Lit <i>roar</i> ³Lit <i>growling</i> ^aLam 1:13, 20f; 2:11; 5:17 ^bJob 3:24; Ps 22:1; 32:3</p> <p>Psalm 38:9 ¹Or <i>known to You</i> ^aPs 10:17 ^bPs 6:6; 102:5</p>	<p>Psalm 38:10 ¹Lit <i>they have</i> ²Lit <i>is not with me</i> ^aPs 31:10 ^bPs 6:7; 69:3; 88:9</p> <p>Psalm 38:11 ¹Or <i>lovers</i> ^aPs 31:11; 88:18 ^bLuke 23:49</p> <p>Psalm 38:12 ¹Lit <i>spoken</i> ^aPs 54:3 ^bPs 140:5 ^cPs 35:4 ^dPs 35:20</p> <p>Psalm 38:13 ^aPs 39:2, 9</p> <p>Psalm 38:15 ¹Or <i>wait for</i> ^aPs 39:7 ^bPs 17:6</p> <p>Psalm 38:16 ^aPs 35:26</p> <p>Psalm 38:17 ¹Lit <i>pain</i> ^aPs 35:15 ^bPs 13:2</p> <p>Psalm 38:18 ¹Or <i>declare</i> ^aPs 32:5 ^b2 Cor 7:9, 10</p>
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Psalm 38:19

¹Or *numerous*

^aPs 18:17

^bPs 35:19

Psalm 38:20

^aPs 35:12

^bPs 109:5; 1 John 3:12

Psalm 38:21

^aPs 22:19; 35:22

Psalm 38:22

^aPs 40:13, 17

^bPs 27:1

Targum

Psa. 38:1 A psalm of David. A handful of incense, a good memorial for Israel. ² O LORD, do not rebuke me in your anger, and do not punish me in your wrath. ³ For your arrows have descended on me, and the blow of your hand rests upon me. ⁴ There is no healing in my body because of your anger, no health in my limbs because of my sin. ⁵ For my sins have mounted past my head; like a heavy burden, they were too heavy for me. ⁶ My wounds stank, they decayed, because of my foolishness. ⁷ I am bent over, I am greatly bowed down; all the day I have gone about in gloom. ⁸ For my loins are filled with burning, and there is no healing in my body. ⁹ I have become faint and I have been humbled greatly; I moaned because of the groaning of my heart. ¹⁰ O LORD, before you is all my desire; and my sighing is not hid from you. ¹¹ My heart has become hot; my strength has left me, and the light of my eyes – even they are not with me. ¹² My friends and companions stood away from the sight of my plague; and my relatives stand far off. ¹³ And those who seek my life have made traps; and those who seek my ruin have uttered lies, and they murmur deceit all the day. ¹⁴ But I am like a deaf man, I will not hear, like a mute who does not open his mouth. ¹⁵ And I have become like a man who has never heard, and there is no rebuke in his mouth. ¹⁶ For in your presence, O LORD, have I prayed; you will accept [my prayer], O LORD my God. ¹⁷ For I said, “Lest they rejoice over me.” When my foot stumbled, they vaunted themselves over me. ¹⁸ For I am prepared for disaster, and my pain is before me always. ¹⁹ For my sin I will relate, I will be troubled by my sin. ²⁰ But my enemies, alive, have grown strong; those who hate me through deceit are numerous. ²¹ And those who repay evil for good oppose me, because I have pursued good. ²² Do not forsake me, O LORD; my God, do not be far from me. ²³ Hasten to my aid, O LORD, my redemption.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

Psalms 38 to 41 are the concluding Psalms of the Psalms' first book. These psalms deal with one theme – the illness that David was afflicted with due to his sins. David tried to learn something from the illnesses and shared these lessons through these psalms.

Superscript

הַזְכִּיר (haz'keer) – means “to remind.” The NASB translates this word as “memorial.” The Theological Word Book of the Old Testament says, “think (about), meditate (upon), pay attention (to); remember, recollect; mention, declare, recite, proclaim, invoke, commemorate, accuse, confess.” David wrote this psalm to pass along what he learned during his illness.

A Psalm of David, for all to know.

Verse One & Two

David acknowledges that his sin is the cause of the illness that he has to live through.

O LORD, do not reprimand me with Your wrath and do not discipline me with your fierce anger.

For Your arrows go deep into me even when Your hand only comes down up me.

Verse three

David understood that it was not an illness that made him feel sick but rather the guilt of his sin.

My flesh has no soundness because of Your indignation; there is no health in my bones because of my sin.

Verse four

David said that a present sin made him recall all of his past sins.

For my iniquities are gone over my head; like an onerous burden, they are too heavy for me.

Verse five

These wounds could have been boils that festered and rotted because his body could not heal them. This illness was caused because his sins had deprived David of his spiritual and moral strength.

My boils fester until they rot because of my sin.

Verse Six

David acknowledged that his physical weakness was because of his moral folly.

**Therefore, I cringed and was greatly bowed down; I went around all day
with my spirit overcast.**

Verse seven

**For my loins are filled with burning, and there is no soundness in my
flesh.**

Verse eight

נְפוּגוֹתַי (n'phugotee) – means “I grow weak,” or “I cease.”

**I grow weak and was sorely oppressed; I groaned from the moaning of
my heart.**

Verse nine

Even though David was a sinner, he still called the LORD his Master. David believed that his sin caused his illness. Instead of becoming angry with the LORD, he acknowledged that the sin was the cause and it was his fault. David took responsibility for his actions.

**My Master, all my yearning is before You, and my sighing is not hidden
from you.**

Verse Ten

**My heart wanders hither and yon, my strength has failed me, even the
light of my eyes is gone from me.**

Verse Eleven and Twelve

David's friends and relatives had abandoned him. This action allowed his enemies to gain new courage to slander and defame him.

My friends and my companions stand aloof from my sufferings, and my kinsmen stand afar off.

Those who seek my life lay snares for me; And those who seek to injure me have threatened destruction, And they devise treachery all day long.

Verses thirteen to sixteen

David said that he kept silent in the face of the slander and defamation from his enemies. He feared that if he would attempt to refute them, he might become provoked and be carried away to do something that the LORD might not approve.

But I, like a deaf man, do not hear; And I am like a mute man who does not open his mouth.

Yes, I am like a man who does not hear, and in whose mouth are no arguments.

For I hope in You, O LORD; You will answer, O Lord my God.

For I said, "May they not rejoice over me, who, when my foot slips, would magnify themselves against me."

Verse seventeen & eighteen

For, as for me, I was prepared for disaster, and my pain is continually before me.

Because I realized my iniquity, and was full of worry because of my sin.

Verses nineteen & twenty

David's enemies were deeply steeped in sin, and its removal did not trouble them. They did not care what sins they committed as long as the sins were directed toward David.

But my enemies are vigorous *and* strong, and many are those who hate me wrongfully.

And those who repay evil for good, they oppose me, because I follow what is good.

Verse twenty-one and twenty-two

David felt confident that he would win the final victory over his enemies because he kept his faith in the LORD.

Do not forsake me, O LORD, you are my God and be close to me.

Hasten to help me; You are my Master and my salvation

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A Psalm of David, for all to know.

O LORD, do not reprimand me with Your wrath and do not discipline me with your fierce anger.

For Your arrows go deep into me even when Your hand only comes down up me.

My flesh has no soundness because of Your indignation; there is no health in my bones because of my sin.

For my iniquities are gone over my head; like an onerous burden, they are too heavy for me.

My boils fester until they rot because of my sin.

Therefore, I cringed and was greatly bowed down; I went around all day with my spirit overcast.

For my loins are filled with burning, and there is no soundness in my flesh. My Master, all my yearning is before You, and my sighing is not hidden from you.

My heart wanders hither and yon, my strength has failed me, even the light of my eyes is gone from me.

My friends and my companions stand aloof from my sufferings, and my kinsmen stand afar off.

Those who seek my life lay snares for me; And those who seek to injure me have threatened destruction, And they devise treachery all day long.

But I, like a deaf man, do not hear; And I am like a mute man who does not open his mouth.

Yes, I am like a man who does not hear, and in whose mouth are no arguments.

For I hope in You, O LORD; You will answer, O Lord my God.

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And those who repay evil for good, they oppose me, because I follow what is good.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

